

Flexcrash

D2.3 Advanced lab-scale testing for crashworthiness estimation of hybrid specimens

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Executive Summary

The document D2.3 “Advanced lab-scale testing for crashworthiness estimation of hybrid specimens” collects the work performed by the Flexcrash consortium in Task 2.3 and is related to Key Exploitable Results (KER) 9 and 10, as listed below.

KER	Result	Category	Target groups	Exploitation route	IPR mechanism	Ownership
9	Advancements in materials characterisation for crashworthiness prediction	Method	Testing labs, industrial organization, road transport industry	Service provision, research, publication	Copyright (for publications) / other IPR mechanisms to be defined	EUT
10	Fatigue tests	Method	Testing labs, industrial organization, road transport industry	Service provision, research, publication	Copyright (for publications) / other IPR mechanisms to be defined	EUT

Deliverable D2.3 details the lab-scale testing performed by the Flexcrash consortium to evaluate the crashworthiness of aluminium structures reinforced with Added Value Functional Features (AVFFs), produced via Directed Energy Deposition with Laser Beam and Powder (DED-LB/P) additive manufacturing. The objective was to validate the mechanical performance of these reinforcements under realistic loading conditions and support further development of crash-tolerant automotive components.

Testing focused on three main areas: fracture toughness, fatigue resistance, and high-speed crash performance. AVFFs showed similar fracture behaviour to the base aluminium alloy, although specimen limitations affected the precision of toughness measurements. A novel, efficient fatigue testing method was introduced, revealing that while AVFFs increased stiffness, they did not significantly improve fatigue life due to crack initiation at the reinforcement. High-speed axial crash tests demonstrated that reinforced crash boxes absorbed energy comparably to unreinforced ones, with no cracking but some weld delamination. 3-point bending tests highlighted that AVFFs notably improved energy absorption under compression (up to 75%) but had limited benefit under tensile loading due to early brittle fracture. Heat treatments improved ductility and energy absorption under compression.

Overall, AVFFs enhance structural performance under specific conditions, particularly compressive stress. These results guide further optimization of reinforcement design for industrial application in lightweight, crash-resistant structures.

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Terminology and Acronyms

AVFFs	Added Value Functional Features
DED-LB/P	Direct Energy Deposition with Laser Beam and Powder
DENT	Double Edge Notched Tensile
DIC	Digital Image Correlation
ED	Extrusion Direction
EDM	Electrical Discharge Machining
EPFM	Elasto-Plastic Fracture Mechanics
EWf	Essential Work of Fracture
FPZ	Fracture Process Zone
KER	Key Exploitable Results
SENB	Single Edge Notched Bending

1. Introduction

While the overall objectives of the project are to predict, design, and manufacture reinforcement structures made of aluminium alloys using DED-LB/P for car body frames, this deliverable focuses specifically on testing the AVFFs to ensure the quality and reproducibility of the reinforcements.

Aluminium structures, while lightweight, have limited energy absorption capacity in the event of a crash. By reinforcing these profiles with geometrically defined structures, it is possible to significantly improve their energy absorption without compromising weight. This deliverable, therefore, concentrates on testing a range of specimens and extruded profiles, both with and without AVFF reinforcements, to validate the improved performance predicted by simulations.

In addition, new testing methodologies have been applied to assess the mechanical behaviour of the reinforced components. One such method evaluates fracture toughness using notched specimens, with the results compared to those obtained through standardised testing protocols. Given that these components are also subject to cyclic loading in service, fatigue resistance must be assessed. To this end, a rapid fatigue testing method, designed to determine the fatigue performance of metallic materials within a few hours, has also been applied to the reinforced specimens.

The results presented in this report will support the validation of simulation outcomes from previous deliverables and inform potential adjustments to the AVFF manufacturing process to further enhance the performance of the reinforced profiles.

2. Development of testing methodologies for AVFFs

2.1 Fracture toughness

As the crash simulations reported in deliverable D2.2 indicate, the extruded profiles should fold to absorb as much energy as possible. This folding behaviour is directly related to the fracture toughness of the material [1]. If a brittle material is chosen, the profiles will fold only slightly, and any defects that form will rapidly propagate, leading to fracture. Conversely, a tougher material requires more energy to generate new fracture surfaces, promoting the complete folding of the extruded profiles and, consequently, greater energy absorption. Therefore, it is crucial to understand the performance of the extruded profiles when selecting the appropriate material.

Fracture toughness was evaluated using the Essential Work of Fracture (EWF) methodology based on Elasto-Plastic Fracture Mechanics (EPFM). The resulting parameter is equivalent to the J-integral and can be measured without the need to monitor crack growth.

The method assumes that the total work of ductile fracture (W_f) can be separated into two terms, the essential work of fracture (W_e) and the non-essential plastic work (W_p). The W_e determines the energy required in the fracture process zone (FPZ) to create new surfaces in the front of the crack tip, while the W_p defines the plastic work dissipated in the outer plastic region surrounding the crack plane. The W_f is obtained by integrating the area under the load vs displacement curve for each specimen tested at a constant displacement rate. The EWF can be determined from a range of specimen geometries, as in tension using Double Edge Notched Tensile (DENT) specimens and in bending

using Single Edge Notched Bending (SENB) specimens. For thin specimens, the DENT is the most suitable because the transverse stress between the notches is tensile, and there is no buckling. Whether the ligament is completely yielded, and the plastic zone is confined to the notched ligament, the w_p is proportional to the plastic volume and w_e is proportional to the fractured area as follows

$$W_f = \int_0^{u_f} P \cdot du = w_e l_0 t_0 + w_p b l_0^2 t_0 \quad (1)$$

where P is the load, u the displacement, u_f the displacement at fracture, β the shape factor that depends on the shape of the plastic zone, t_0 the specimen thickness and l_0 the initial ligament length. Equation 1 can be rearranged, allowing the experimental determination of the EWF according to equation 2, which defines the specific essential work of fracture, w_e , as the intercept and the specific non-essential work of fracture, $w_p b$, as the slope.

$$\frac{W_f}{l_0 t_0} = w_f = w_e + w_p b l_0 \quad (2)$$

By testing multiple DENT specimens with different ligament lengths it is possible to determine the w_e by plotting the w_f against l_0 as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 1. DENT specimen for the EWF tests: W_f for different ligament lengths and plot of w_f vs l_0 , the intercept gives the specific work of fracture, w_e .

The EWF method allows for experimental separation of the energetic contributions from crack initiation and propagation, in contrast to the EPFM toughness value, J_c , which is a measure of cracking initiation. Thus, when there is a relevant contribution from crack propagation after initiation w_e better describes the steady-state crack propagation resistance. The specific work for fracture initiation, w_f^i , is obtained by integrating the load vs displacement curve up to the onset of crack propagation, w_f^i , for different ligament lengths as follows

$$w_f^i = \frac{1}{l_0 t_0} \int_0^{u_i} P \cdot du \quad (3)$$

where u_i is the displacement at the initiation of crack propagation. It is worth noticing that w_f^i is independent of the ligament length, and the mean value of w_f^i determines the w_e^i as illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the determination of specific work of fracture at the onset of propagation and variation of w_f^i as a function of ligament length.

The reported values for thin ductile sheets have an important contribution from necking, having a high influence from the sheet thickness. Therefore, the measured w_e and w_e^i are not a material intrinsic property and are only valid for the evaluated sheet thickness.

For the extruded profiles, fatigue pre-cracked DENT specimens of 90 x 40 mm were used. Initial notches were machined by electrical discharge machining (EDM). The fatigue pre-cracks were nucleated at the notch root by using a Rumul resonance fatigue testing machine and following the recommendations of the ASTM E1820. The cracks with a minimum length of 1 mm determined the different ligament lengths (l_0), ranging from 8 to 16 mm. At least 2 specimens per ligament were machined at 90° concerning the extrusion direction (ED).

Figure 3. DENT specimen geometry and detail of the fatigue pre-crack at the notch root. ED: Extrusion direction The dimensions are expressed in mm.

The pre-cracked specimens were tested up to fracture in a 250 kN universal testing machine, Instron 5585H, equipped with a digital video extensometer. The testing conditions were established according to the CWA 17793:2021 protocol for EWF testing [2]. The constant crosshead testing speed was set at 1 mm/min. The load-displacement measurements were performed using the video extensometer, using initial marks separated by 25 mm. The crack initiation was detected by using a high-resolution video

camera synchronised with the testing machine. The w_f^i was determined for at least 1 specimen of each ligament length, and the w_e^i was determined as the average of those w_f^i values.

For validation purposes of the EWF measurements, a full field strain analysis was performed on the surface of the ligament area to check that the ligament was fully yielded before crack initiation (Figure 4). The specimens were painted with a stochastic pattern and recorded using a high-resolution video camera at a frame rate of 5 images/second for a later Digital Image Correlation (DIC) analysis through GOM correlate software. The facet size and step size of 13 and 11 pixels, respectively, were used in the software.

Figure 4. Full-field analysis of the ligament area to assess yielding before crack initiation.

Considering the fracture toughness values observed in the extruded profiles, a testing strategy has been developed to determine the fracture toughness of the AVFFs printed on the extruded profiles. Following a similar strategy to the EWF methodology, different notches of 0,5 mm and 1 mm were machined by EDM on the AVFFs (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Flat specimens with AVFFs for fracture toughness tests.

The reinforcement attached to flat aluminium specimens was tested in a 3-point bending configuration (Figure 6a) using a span of 29 mm and a load rate of 1 mm/min. The tests were carried out in an Instron 5585H equipped with the DIC system to monitor crack propagation through the AVFF, as shown in Figure 6b.

Figure 6. a) Fracture toughness test setup for AVFFs and b) Strain at fracture initiation for the AVFF with a notch of 0.5 mm.

Figure 7 shows the load-displacement curves for the aluminium plates with notched AVFFs of 0.5 mm and 1 mm long. The AVFFs exhibit a dual ductile-brittle fracture behaviour observed in the load-displacement curves. The fracture toughness of the AVFF was determined following the ASTM E399 procedure by defining a K_Q value. As reported in Table 1, the fracture toughness of the extruded profile 6063 T5 and the AVFF shows similar fracture behaviour. To carry out such a comparison, the fracture toughness of the 6063 T5 for the crack initiation has been converted to the K_Q value following the procedure defined in the ASTM E399. It should be noted that the comparison of these results in terms of fracture toughness is only indicative, as the DENT specimens were pre-cracked, while the AVFF specimens were only notched. Proper determination of fracture toughness must be carried out using pre-cracked specimens; however, the small dimensions of the AVFF made this impossible. Therefore, the fracture toughness values obtained for the AVFF could be lower if pre-cracked specimens are used instead of notched ones.

Table 1. Fracture toughness results for the extruded profile and the AVFF.

Material	W_e^i [kJ/m ²]	K_Q [MPa m ^{1/2}]
6063 T5 (pre-cracked)	94 ± 7	81
AVFF (notched)	-	71 ± 12

Figure 7. Load vs. Displacement curves for a) DENT specimens and b) notched specimens with AVFFs profiles.

2.2 Fatigue resistance

The fatigue resistance of the reinforced specimens shown in Figure 5 was determined using the same testing setup used for the fracture toughness tests. To assess the effect of the AVFF on the fatigue performance, two different conditions were characterised: flat specimens of 150 x 20 mm with and without AVFF.

It is well known that fatigue tests following the ISO 1099 standard are both time- and material-consuming, which can limit the development of new strategies and technologies such as those explored in this work. For this reason, a new fatigue testing method is proposed to evaluate the fatigue performance of reinforced specimens more efficiently, requiring only three specimens.

The method, known as the stiffness method and described in CWA 18107-2:2024 [3], involves applying a stepwise increasing load until the specimen fractures, as illustrated in Figure 8. Between each load increment block, the strain response of the specimen is measured by applying a constant load P_c . The specimens were tested at 3-point bending using a stress ratio of 0,1 and a frequency of 15 Hz, starting with a maximum load of 100 N, and increasing by 25 N in each subsequent fatigue block of 6000 cycles. The stiffness (or strain response) was evaluated by applying a fixed load of 200 N and measuring the displacement using the LVDT of the MTS testing machine.

Figure 8. Stepwise loading blocks used until the fracture of the specimen.

The increase in displacement for the P_c load indicates the accumulation of fatigue damage in the specimen, enabling a straightforward assessment of the material's fatigue resistance. As shown in Figure 9, plotting the measured displacement against the maximum load applied in each fatigue block reveals an exponential increase in the displacement, reflecting the progression of fatigue damage. To estimate the fatigue limit, this progression can be represented using a log-log plot, which helps identify a change in slope, a characteristic marker of significant fatigue damage in the material. This inflexion point correlates well with the fatigue limit (σ_f), as proposed by Parareda [4].

Figure 9. Measured displacement vs. maximum load for each fatigue block, shown in (a) linear and (b) log-log plots. The grey arrow indicates the change in slope.

Table 2 presents the results obtained for the two tested conditions: reinforced and non-reinforced specimens. While the use of AVFFs increases the stiffness of the specimen, the fatigue performance of both configurations is comparable. The stress in the external layer of the tested specimens was calculated using the 3-point bending formula.

$$\sigma_f = \frac{3FL}{2bd^2} \tag{1}$$

where F is the applied load, L is the support span, b is the width of the specimen and d is the thickness of the material.

This outcome is likely because, in a three-point bending setup, the AVFF may reinforce the specimen structurally but can also serve as a crack initiation point at the interface between the aluminium sheet surface and the AVFF root. These differing fracture mechanisms are illustrated in Figure 10: the non-reinforced specimen shows no visible cracking, while the reinforced specimen exhibits crack initiation beginning at the surface of the AVFF.

Table 2. Fatigue results for the reinforced and non-reinforced specimens.

Condition	P_f [N]	σ_f [MPa]
Base material	222	215
Reinforced material	204 ± 24	197 ± 24

Figure 10. Tested fatigue specimens a) without and b) with reinforcement.

3. Mechanical tests

3.1 High-speed tests

To evaluate the energy-absorbing capacity and crashworthiness of the produced hybrid specimens with different AVFF patterns, crash boxes for axial compression testing were manufactured. The crash boxes with straight line and fishbone AVFF patterns are described in deliverable D2.2 and are shown in Figure 29. As a reference, a box without AVFF was tested as well.

The crash tests were performed at a speed of 10 m/s in a high-speed machine, Instron VHS160/100-20. The high-speed machine was complemented with two high-speed cameras, Phantom Vision v1610 and v2512, to enable monitoring of folding formation and full-field deformation measurement by applying 3D Digital Image Correlation (3D-DIC, GOM-ARAMIS). All crash boxes were prepared with a speckle pattern by applying black and white spray paint. The crash boxes were slightly pre-bent at the top to help trigger the folding in the view of the cameras. By adding this optical equipment and evaluation methods, the plastic deformations, crack initiations and propagations during the compression can be detected. A frame rate of 10000 fps was used, resulting in a spatial resolution of 640 x 800 pixels.

Figure 11 presents the setup with the two cameras and a tested crash box. Two valid tests of crash boxes with the straight ribbed AVFF pattern and three boxes with the fishbone AVFF pattern were conducted. In addition to the deformation fields, the force and intrusion histories were measured with the high-speed machine and DIC.

Figure 11: High-speed axial compression test setup with stereo high-speed cameras.

Images from the high-speed testing of a crash box without AVFF prepared with a randomised speckle pattern are presented in Figure 12, together with an overlay to track strains during deformation.

Figure 12: High-speed imaging of a crash box without AVFF. Raw image (left) and with strain field overlay (right).

The reference crash box without AVFF after dynamic axial compression is presented in Figure 13. No visible cracks were detected post-experiment, and 4 clear folds were visible. Two crash boxes with the straight ribbed AVFF after crushing are presented in Figure 14. No cracks were detected in either of the boxes, and three clear folds were visible. However, some delaminations of the AVFF welds were detected. The results were similar for the crash boxes with the fishbone AVFF presented in Figure 15, except for creating 4 folds instead of 3.

Figure 13: Crushed crash box without AVFF. No cracks were detected, and four clear folds were visible.

Figure 14: Crushed crash boxes with straight ribbed AVFF. No cracks were detected, and three clear folds were visible. Some delaminations of AVFF welds were detected.

Figure 15: Crushed crash boxes with fishbone AVFF. No cracks were detected, and four clear folds were visible. Some delaminations of AVFF welds were detected.

Load curves for the tested crash boxes are presented, and their absorbed energy is presented in Figure 16. The energy absorbed is calculated as the cumulative integration of the load curves over the crush distance. There is no significant difference between the different crash boxes, regardless of the addition or shape of AVFF. A summary of the individual crash tests is presented in Table 3.

Figure 16: Load curves for the crash boxes (left) and the energy absorbed for each box (right). No significant difference could be seen between the different samples.

Table 3. Summary of the individual crash box test results performed under dynamic axial compression.

Crash box	AVFF	Speed [m/s]	Energy absorbed [J]	Cracks
Sample #1	-	10	3118	No
Sample #2	Ribbed	10	3188	No
Sample #3	Ribbed	10	3146	No
Sample #4	Fishbone	10	3149	No
Sample #5	Fishbone	10	3189	No
Sample #6	Fishbone	10	3185	No

3.2 Mechanical tests

To design complex reinforcements, it is important to know the mechanical properties of each subcomponent (substrate material only, substrate with reinforcement on tensile side and substrate with reinforcement on compression side). The challenge is that it is not possible to extract tensile specimens from the small reinforcements that are built up in this project. That is why the solution was to use 3-point bending tests with simple straight reinforcements with the dimensions 110 x 2 x 2.5 mm on thin substrate plates with 150 x 20 x 1.5 mm (Figure 17).

All experiments were done under the following testing conditions:

- Analysis limited to 30 mm in deformation due to friction with roller holders.
- Deformation speed 80 mm/s.
- Distance between rollers 52 mm.

Figure 17. Test machine for 3-point bending test with a specimen without reinforcement.

In order to show the changes compared to the initial state, 1.5 mm-thick samples without reinforcement structure were tested first. The results from the reference set can be seen in Figure 18. The five samples showed uniform results with each other.

Figure 18. Comparison of 3-point bending test results with and without reinforcement.

The cross-sectional area of the samples with reinforcement increases by 16 %. The length of the reinforcement was long enough to cover all the areas exposed to deformation in the test setup. The 3-point bending tests with the reinforcement on the tensile side show a significant improvement in the required deformation energy only in the first 4 mm of deformation. After the cracking of the reinforcement, the substrate acts alone and produces results like those without reinforcement. This shows that the heat-affected zone has a low impact. At around 18 mm of deformation length, the crack through the reinforcement propagates into the substrate, and the sample partially breaks completely before reaching the maximum deformation length. The sample bends in a V-shape at the breaking point of the reinforcing structure. As a result, the compression punch of the test system touches the sample at off-centre contacts, and the results are more spread out.

The results from the 3-point bending tests with reinforcement on the compression side show a slight increase in variability between samples compared to the uniform results

from the substrates-only tests. Also, compared to the substrate-only results, the samples with reinforcement on the compression side show a 75% force increase during deformation (see Table 4). The DED-LB/P material is more brittle than the substrate and shows visible cracks after testing.

Table 4. Comparison of the energy absorption from test samples with and without reinforcement.

	Substrate only [J]	Tensile AVFF [J]	Compression AVFF [J]
Average energy 30 mm	9,79 ± 0,07	10,02 ± 0,77 (+2,4%)	17,21 ± 0,82 (+75,8%)
Average energy 20 mm	6,92 ± 0,04	7,27 ± 0,21 (+5,1%)	12,10 ± 0,54 (+74,8%)

By comparison, the results from the 3-point bending tests a significant increase in energy absorption only appears when the reinforcement is on the compression side of the substrate. The heat-affected zone seems to have a low impact on results compared to the results from the tests with reinforcement on the tensile side after cracking of the AVFF.

In the next step, a heat treatment was performed to increase the elongation at fracture of DED-LB/P material. The result comparison of these experiments is shown in Figure 19 and Table 5. The heat treatment leads to a reduction in the absorbed deformation energy and does not increase the elongation at break of the reinforcement structure, but that of the substrate material.

Figure 19. Comparison of 3-point bending test results with and without reinforcement and heat treatment.

Table 5. Comparison of the energy absorption from test samples with and without reinforcement and additional heat treatment.

	Substrate only [J]	Tensile AVFF + HT [J]	Compression AVFF + HT [J]
Average energy 30 mm	9,79 ± 0,07	10,17 ± 0,49 (+3,9%)	13,05 ± 0,88 (+33,3%)
Average energy 20 mm	6,92 ± 0,04	6,07 ± 0,25 (-12,3%)	9,11 ± 0,55 (+31,6%)

To summarise, the results of the 3-point bending tests with and without heat treatment are as follows:

1. AlSi10Mg reinforcement structures can be manufactured by DED-LB/P on 1,5 mm thin substrates with relatively low thermal deformations and HAZ on the substrate.
2. When reinforcement structures are subjected to tensile stresses, the brittle DED-LB/P material cracks soon, leading to a low energy absorption improvement.
3. When reinforcement structures are subjected to compressive stresses, the specimens withstand higher forces and overall increased energy absorption.
4. Heat treatments increase the ductility of the structure, but also increase the energy absorption.

4. Conclusions

Successfully advanced lab-scale testing procedures have been developed and applied to evaluate the crashworthiness of hybrid aluminium structures reinforced with AVFFs using DED-LB/P additive manufacturing. Key findings include:

- AVFFs demonstrated fracture toughness comparable to the base aluminium alloy (6063 T5), though the testing method had limitations due to specimen size.
- Reinforcement did not significantly alter fracture behaviour under the tested conditions.
- A novel stiffness-based fatigue testing method provided an efficient assessment of fatigue properties.
- While AVFFs increased specimen stiffness, they did not significantly enhance fatigue life due to potential crack initiation at the AVFF.
- Hybrid crash boxes showed similar energy absorption to non-reinforced ones.
- No cracks were detected, though AVFF weld delaminations occurred.
- AVFF geometry (straight vs. fishbone) had a limited impact on energy absorption.
- Reinforcements under compression increased energy absorption significantly (~75%).
- Under tensile loading, AVFFs cracked early, offering limited benefit.
- Heat treatment improved ductility and moderate gains in energy absorption, especially under compression.

Overall, AVFFs enhance structural performance mainly under compressive stresses, with limited effect under tensile or fatigue conditions. Future work will refine manufacturing and design parameters to optimise crashworthiness and mechanical performance in real-world applications.

5. References

- [1] Frómeta, D., Lara, A., Molas, S., Casellas, D., Rehrl, J., Suppan, C., ... & Calvo, J. (2019). On the correlation between fracture toughness and crash resistance of advanced high strength steels. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 205, 319-332.
- [2] European Committee for Standardization. *Test Method for Determination of the Essential Work of Fracture of Thin Ductile Metallic Sheets*; CEN-CENELE: Brussels, Belgium, 2021.
- [3] European Committee for Standardization. *Advanced fatigue testing methods-Part 2: Stiffness method.*; CEN-CENELE: Brussels, Belgium, 2024.
- [4] Parareda, S., Casellas, D., Mares, M., & Mateo, A. (2023). A damage-based uniaxial fatigue life prediction method for metallic materials. *Materials & design*, 231, 112056.